

Volume 13, Issues 1 & 2, March, 2026

Geo-Studies Forum

An International Journal of Environmental & Policy Issues

*A Publication of the Department of Geography
and Environmental Management
University of Ilorin*

GEO-STUDIES FORUM

A Publication of

**THE DEPARTMENT OF GEOGRAPHY AND
ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT,
FACULTY OF SOCIAL SCIENCE,
UNIVERSITY OF ILORIN,
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VOLUME 13, ISSUES 1&2, MARCH, 2026

ISSN: 1596-4116

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KNOWLEDGE OF ROAD SIGNS AND COMPLIANCE OF INTRA-URBAN COMMERCIAL BUS DRIVERS WITH TRAFFIC REGULATIONS IN ILORIN, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Safety of lives and properties is crucial to both drivers and passengers on the road. Despite various efforts by governments at different levels to ensure safety on Nigerian roads, road traffic violations and traffic accidents especially involving commercial vehicle drivers are still very common. This study focused on investigating commercial bus drivers' compliance with traffic regulations in Ilorin with a view to determining whether there is link between their knowledge of traffic signs and level of compliance. This study employed purposive and simple random sampling techniques to draw a sample of 158 bus drivers used for the study. Descriptive statistics and Chi-square were used to analyse the data. The results reveal that the mean age of the drivers was 44 years, married (69.0%) and majority (67.09%) of the sampled bus drivers does not have valid driver's license. Result of the Chi-square shows $\chi^2_{\text{calculated}} (35.1657) > \chi^2_{\text{statistics}} (5.991)$ at 95% confidence level signifying that knowledge of road signs influence bus drivers' compliance with traffic regulation as safety measure. Therefore, it is concluded that compliance with traffic rules would enhance safety among commercial bus drivers in the study. This study recommends more stringent measures to ensure that only those who are qualified are licensed to drive on Nigerian roads. There should also be periodic road safety sensitization for commercial drivers by relevant road safety agencies to ensure familiarity with traffic signs and regulations for effective compliance to reduce road crashes.*

Keywords: Commercial bus drivers, compliance, road signs, traffic regulations, Ilorin.

INTRODUCTION

In developing countries, privately operated public transportation play very important role in providing mobility for majority of the population. Their services are particularly important in the cities where government mass transit services are often limited. The prevalence of these informal and semi-formal transport services play a critical role in

economic development by providing essential coverage for movement of goods and services (Nwachukwu et al., 2025). Nevertheless, these informal commercial transport services are often characterized by unreliability, less predictable fares, poor quality and dangerous safety conditions (Afolabi, 2015; Shittu, 2024).

In Nigeria, road transportation is one of the most commonly used modes of transportation, probably as a result of its convenience and affordability. The vast majority of passengers and petty goods in Nigeria are transported by road means (Filani, 2003; Hashidu *et al.*; 2020; Kolo *et al.*, 2021). Government at different levels (especially, at federal and state) have made remarkable efforts to improve the free flow of vehicular movement and road safety. Some of these efforts include deliberate policy on road construction through Ministry of Works and Housing; establishment of Federal Road Maintenance Agency (FERMA) in charge of rehabilitation and maintenance of federal roads; and the establishment of agencies for the enforcement and maintenance of law and order on the roads. The agencies include Federal Road Safety Commission (FRSC) with the responsibility of monitoring the speed of motorists, checking of vehicles documents, rendering quick response and assistance for accident victims especially on emergency; Vehicle Inspection Office (VIO); and the Traffic Police Officers' wing of the Nigeria Police Force (Afolabi, 2015). Road signs and traffic regulations are also put in place by government to provide some basic information to guide the operations of road users. However, despite all these efforts by governments to improve compliance to traffic regulations and guarantee safety on the roads, road traffic accidents and resultant fatalities have continued to constitute major health and developmental problem in Nigeria (Afolabi, 2015; Gbadamosi, 2015; Olakulehin, *et al.*, 2019; Wole, *et al.*, 2024).

This study is premised on the principle of deterrence. Deterrence is the act of discouraging someone or group of individuals from doing something through a set aside punishment. It has been a long-standing measure that became popular in 1960s. Thereafter, various deterrence theories

and models have been put forward (Beyleveld, 1979; Gibbs, 1975; Homel, 1988). The philosophy behind deterrence is such that the risk to the lawbreaker must be made so severe such that the violator will have more to lose for the offence. For instance, Muhammed *et al.* (2015) posited that violators of traffic regulations usually perceived it as minor offence.

The principle of deterrence is found to be relevant to this study if compliance to traffic regulations would be enforced optimally. Hence, it is used as a background principle upon which the study unfolds. Deterrence as a mode to address compliance with traffic regulation could be more effective among commercial bus drivers in the study area. It considers sanction prepared by the concerned authorities for violation of traffic regulation to be severe in such that it prohibits law breaker from violating the laws, and ensure total compliance to reduce roadcrashes to the barest minimum.

Various studies in Nigeria have highlighted the high incidence of road traffic crashes in the country (Sumaila, 2013; Gbadamosi, 2015; Yusuf, 2015; Afolabi and Gbadamosi, 2017; Innocent, 2021). Various factors contributing to traffic accidents severity of injuries in the country have also been identified. These include over speeding, driving under the influence of alcohol, bad roads and widespread non-compliance to traffic regulations. Some other studies have also examined compliance with road safety regulations particularly on the usage of seat belt among commercial drivers and usage of helmet among commercial motorcyclist (Yakubu, 2015; Usman and Abdulkadir, 2019; Usman and Toluwase, 2024).

Despite the research efforts that are complementing the regulations put in place by government to improve safety on the roads,

traffic accident has continued to be a major problem in Nigeria. This has also become an issue of global concern. The fundamental question is that, do these commercial drivers comply with traffic regulations? Adequate compliance with road signs and traffic regulations are expected to reduce road crash to the barest minimum. This will not only guarantee safety of lives and property of road users, but also enhance economic activities.

Furthermore, being one of the major transportation medium in Ilorin, empirical evidence that examine the compliance of road signs and traffic regulation among commercial bus drivers has not been accessed in study area. Meanwhile, knowledge on the attitude of the drivers with respect to compliance with traffic regulations will offer a viable insight on the appropriate policy to be

adopted for sufficient safety. It is based on the aforementioned that this study focused on investigating the knowledge of road signs and compliance of intra-urban commercial bus drivers with traffic regulations in Ilorin. The specific objectives were to: assess the commercial bus driver’s knowledge of road signs, investigate the drivers’ compliance with traffic regulations and examine the implications on road safety in the area.

STUDY AREA

The study was conducted in Ilorin, the state capital of Kwara State. The State has common internal boundary with Niger State in the North, Kogi State in the East, Oyo, Ekiti and Osun State in the South, and it borders with Benin Republic in the west. Ilorin is located between the latitudes 8° 30' North of the equator and longitudes 4° 35' East of the Greenwich meridian.

Figure 1: Map of Kwara State showing Ilorin (Nigeria showing Kwara State as inset)

Source: Adapted from Oluyemi, *et al.* (2016).

It has an area of about 100km² (Olaniran 2002). It is located within North Central Geopolitical Zones and it has a population of 781,934 (NPC, 2006). However, her projected population based on 2.8% growth rate was 1,285,423 as at the year 2024. Ilorin operates an intra-city public transportation on the major roads within the metropolis. The main forms of commercial transiting within the city are mini buses, long buses, taxis, commercial tricycles, popularly called "Keke NAPEP" or "Keke Maruwa" and commercial motorcycles that is commonly called "Okada". However, this study focused on mini and long buses used for commercial purpose.

MATERIALS AND METHODS
SOURCES AND METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION

Both primary and secondary data were used for the study. Primary data were obtained through semi-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered to commercial bus drivers at the major parks within Ilorin city. This was supplemented by interview schedule. A familiarization platform was created by way of presenting the purpose of the research study to the drivers' union (National Union of Road Transportation Workers- NURTW) executives led by the Chapter chairmen and the Union Officials in each of the selected parks. Through this process, better understanding of drivers' perceptions about traffic law compliance and the factors influencing their driving attitude were established. In order to improve the validity of the survey tools, a Pilot test survey was carried out among 30 randomly selected bus drivers outside the sample location prior to implementation of the survey. With the help of specialist in relevant field of studies, the questionnaire was adjusted accordingly.

SAMPLE SIZE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

The study used purposive and simple random sampling techniques to draw a three-stage sampling for the study. This is because the targeted respondents were difficult to reach outside their loading points. The sampling techniques are convenient and easy to draw sample. Data for this study were drawn among the commercial bus drivers that registered with the Kwara State Chapter of NURTW at the various loading points in the study area.

Purposive selection of the major intra-city loading points within Ilorin were identified and used at the first stage. These loading points prominently serve as take off and alighting points for passengers and loading of petty goods such as food stuffs and stationery among intra-urban commercial buses operating within the city. At the second stage, a purposive selection of Idi Ape, Ile Film, Kwara Polytechnic Gate, and Tanke loading points were made. This was based on the large volume of commercial driving activities with buses in these locations as informed by the preliminary survey conducted. Idi Ape loading point has a total of 57 registered bus drivers, Ile Film loading point has a total of 84 registered bus drivers, a total of 61 registered bus drivers at Kwara State polytechnic Gate and Tanke loading point has a total of 66 bus drivers that registered with the union as at the year 2023. These make a total of 268 registered bus drivers in the selected loading points (unpublished document). At the third and final stage, questionnaire was randomly administered to a total of 161 sample respondent proportionate to size in each park based on the formula adopted from Yamane Taro (1967) and sampling intensity of 5% (equation 1). This is to minimize error and bias.

The formula is given as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + (e^2)N} \text{----- (1)}$$

Where:

n= Estimated Sample size

N = Definitive population of registered bus drivers in the study area.

e = margin of error (0.05)

By using the formula in equation (1), the sample size (n) was computed out of the total

registered bus drivers in the study area. Finally, the respondents were selected from the list using simple random Sampling technique. However, 158 of them had complete information, and were used for this study.

Table 1: Distribution of Sampled Respondents

Name of Loading Point	Number of Registered Bus Drivers	Estimated Sample size in each location
Idi-Ape	57	34
Ile Film	84	50
Kwara State polytechnic Gate	61	57
Tanke	66	40
Total	268	161

Source: Field Survey, 2023

METHODS OF DATA ANALYSIS

Descriptive statistics that involve the use of frequency, tables, percentage and arithmetic mean were used to describe the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents. These were also used to analyse respondents’ knowledge of road signs and their compliance with traffic regulations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF

COMMERCIAL BUS DRIVERS IN ILORIN

The socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents are presented in Table 2. The study revealed that 36.7% of the respondents fall within the age range of 41 to 50 years, and 31.0% of them are between the age of 31 and 40 years. Also, 8.23% of the respondents were above 60 years of age, and 19.62% of the bus drivers’ fall between 51 and 60 years of age, while just 4.4% of them were not more than 30 years old. The maximum age was 72 years while the mean age was 44 years.

Table 2: Socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents (n=158)

Variable		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percent	Years
Age	≤ 30 years	7	4.4	4.4	Min=25 max=72 Mean=44
	31- 40 years	49	31.0	35.4	
	41- 50 years	58	36.7	72.2	
	51- 60 years	31	19.62	91.8	
	> 60 years	13	8.23	100.0	
Education level	No formal education	2	1.3	1.3	
	Quranic education	29	18.4	19.6	
	Primary education	64	40.5	60.1	
	Secondary education	45	28.5	88.6	
	Tertiary education	18	11.4	100.0	
Marital status	Single	23	14.6	14.6	
	Married	109	69.0	83.5	
	Widowed	21	13.3	96.8	
	Separated/divorced	5	3.2	100.0	
Possession of valid driver's license	No	106	67.09	67.1	
	Yes	52	32.91	100.0	
Driving school training	No	99	62.7	62.7	
	Yes	59	37.3	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The study also revealed that majority (80.3%) of the bus drivers had one form of formal education or the other while remaining 19.7% of the bus drivers do not have formal education. Education acquisition could increase the respondents' potential in assessing information regarding rules and regulation through reading leaflet of road safety and listening to news that is related to safety guide. This implies that most of the respondents were within the active age and can effectively participate in bus driving. The results also indicate that most of the drivers are educated to some level and likely to have

better understanding of traffic regulations. This is in line with the findings of Anene (2022) who held that age, driving experience and educational background play an important role in drivers' understanding of traffic signs and symbols.

With respect to the marital status of the respondents, the study revealed that larger proportions (69.0%) of the respondents were married and 16.4% of them were single. The percentage of respondents that were either separated or divorced was 3.2% while the remaining 13.3% of the respondents were

widowed. This explains the importance of family responsibilities as it might reflect in the compliance attitude of bus drivers to traffic regulations. Marital status is another variable that can influence commercial drivers' compliance to traffic regulations. High proportion of married people among the respondents might imply more responsibility and more dependency rate.

On the possession of valid driver's license, majority (67.09%) of the sampled drivers do not have valid driver's license. Drivers with valid driver's license are more likely to comply with traffic regulations compared to drivers who do not possess valid driver's license. Possession of driver's license is a confirmation that the FRSC has certified the driver as having the knowledge of traffic regulations and the skill to operate the vehicle on the road. Therefore, those who have driver's license are expected to be more compliant to traffic rules and regulations.

The distribution of respondents in accordance with driving school training is presented in Table 2. The study revealed that larger proportion (62.7%) of the sampled bus drivers did not pass through any officially accredited driving school. Also, only 37.3% of the sample respondents attended driving school training. Driving training acquisition enhances effective driving and compliance to traffic regulations which could reduce the road

crash. Attending an officially accredited driving school and receiving a certificate is one of the requirements for obtaining a driver's license in Nigeria. However, many people often circumvent this requirement to obtain drivers license with the connivance of some regulatory officials. This may be the explanation for many of the respondents possessing driver's license without driving school training.

KNOWLEDGE OF ROAD SIGNS AND ADHERENCE TO TRAFFIC REGULATIONS BY BUS DRIVERS IN ILORIN

COMMERCIAL DRIVERS' KNOWLEDGE OF ROAD SIGNS

As seen in Table 3, knowledge of some of the road signs was found to be high among the drivers. Table 3 shows that "Stop for Police Check" (91.77%), "Approaching 'T' Junction" (76.88%), "One Way Drive" (75.32%) and "Intersection with Minor Road" (70.44%) recorded higher awareness among the drivers. The high proportion recorded for Stop for Police Check is expected because of the physical presence of Police officers at such checking points. As such the drivers would be forced to slow down their vehicle or even stop depending on existing situation. Also, One Way drive is often physically enforced by police and other road safety officers in Nigerian cities. This could be responsible for the high proportion of drivers who indicate awareness of this road sign.

Table 3: Commercial Drivers’ Knowledge of Road Signs

Road Signs(I)	Aware	Not Aware
Zebra crossing	74 (46.83%)	84 (53.16%)
Approaching T-Junction	121 (76.88%)	34 (23.42%)
Traffic Light	124 (78.48%)	34 (21.52%)
Pedestrian Crossing	101 (63.92%)	57 (36.17%)
No parking	76 (48.10%)	82 (51.89%)
Stop for Police Check	145 (91.77%)	13 (8.23%)
Intersection with minor road	112 (70.49%)	46 (29.11%)
No U-turn	121 (76.58%)	37 (23.42%)
One way drive	119 (75.32%)	39 (24.68%)
No over taking	66 (41.77%)	92 (58.23%)

Source: Field survey, 2023

However, the result in Table 3 further show that only 46. 83% of the respondents are aware of the function of the Zebra Crossing. Other road signs that recorded low awareness among the drivers are “No Overtaking” (41.77%) and “No Parking” (48.10%). These are all important road traffic signs that are vital for reducing road crashes. Therefore lack of knowledge on these importance road signs among the drivers will increase the possibility of violation by the drivers. The implication of unawareness about Zebra crossing is the high risk of vehicle collision with pedestrians. For example, Nwachukwu (2026) noted that it is common to see drivers speed past at zebra crossings in Nigerian cities, without giving

consideration to pedestrians. Furthermore, wrong overtaking has been identified as major causes of road accidents in Nigeria (Oke, 2013). On-road parking has also been closely associated with traffic congestion and traffic accidents in Nigerian cities (Oluwaseyi *et al.*, 2014).

ADHERENCE TO TRAFFIC REGULATIONS

Table 4 reveals various traffic regulations and the commercial bus drivers’ compliance with of each of these traffic regulations in the study area. The result in Table 4 shows that only 25.95 of the drivers make use of seat belt while driving.

Table 4: Adherence to Traffic Regulations by Commercial Bus Drivers

Compliance with traffic regulations (II)	Yes	No
Use of seat belt	41(25.95%)	117(74.05%)
Use of valid driver’s license	49(31.01%)	109(68.99%)
Attends driving school training	36(22.78%)	122(77.22%)
Possess vehicle particulars	51(32.28%)	107(67.72%)
Maitaining the maximum speed limit by law	82(51.90%)	76(48.10%)
Functional Horn	64(40.51%)	94(59.49%)
Functional trafficator light	80(50.63%)	78(49.37%)
Maintaining the maximum number of passengers by law	99(62.66%)	59(37.34%)
Adherence to right overtaking	121(76.58%)	37(23.42%)

Source: Field survey, 2023.

As also indicated in Table 4, very small proportion (31.01%) of the drivers had valid drivers license as at the time of the survey. Furthermore, only 22.78% indicated attending driving school before engagement as commercial drivers. The possession of valid particulars was also very low (32.28%). As also shown in Table 4 compliance with other important requirements to fulfilled before a vehicle can be operated including functional horn (40%) and Trafficator light (50.63%) were low. Possession of valid drivers' license is an important requirement for operating a vehicle on the road. Therefore, non-possession in not only illegal but indicates that these drivers constitute serious risk to themselves, the passengers and other road users. Not attending the mandatory training at an accredited training school before driving also increases the risk of causing accident. These findings are in line with those of Okafor et al. (2014) who observed very low level of formal drivers' training among commercial bus drivers in Lagos, Nigeria. Unlicensed drivers are more likely to be involved in road crashes and are more likely to engage in other unsafe driving behaviours like speeding and not wearing seat belt (Martin-delosReyes et al., 2021).

ii. Reduced safety for pedestrians: poor understanding of road signs like pedestrian (zebra) crossing as observed in the study increases the risk of pedestrians being knocked down, causing injury or death. Generally, pedestrians are often belittled by motor vehicle drivers and this increases their risk of being involved in traffic accidents (Macioszek et al., 2023). According to the World Bank (2014) pedestrians constitute 44% of road deaths in sub-Saharan Africa. Pedestrian injuries and fatalities has also become an important public health issue in Nigeria. For example according to FRSC ()

IMPLICATIONS FOR ROAD SAFETY IN ILORIN

Road signs and regulations are specifically designed to deliver important information and used to promote safe driving on the road. These signs and rules are expected to govern how road users should behave on the road and ensure safety for all road users. Therefore poor knowledge of road signs as observed among the drivers has a lot of implications for road safety in the area.

i. Increased risk of road accidents and fatalities: traffic signs and regulations are envisioned to prevent accident thus; lack of understanding or ignorance of vital road signs greatly raises the possibility of accidents in the area. For instance, according to Afolabi and Gbadamosi (2017) human factor, particularly disregard for road signs constitute major factor responsible for road accidents in Nigeria. In 2021 a total of 394 road traffic crashes were reported in Kwara State, involving 2,521 people, 246 deaths and 1,357 injured (FRSC, 2022). Some of these accidents could be attributable to ignorance of road signs and traffic regulations among drivers.

pedestrians accounted for 22% of road traffic fatalities in Nigeria in 2020.

ii. Traffic violation and risky behaviour: drivers with low understanding of traffic regulatory and warning signs are more likely to violate traffic laws. This is because drivers who cannot identify or understand signs used to promote safety on the road are more likely to make illegal dangerous maneuvers such as illegal U-turn, speeding, running red lights and failing to yield at pedestrian crossings.

iv. Traffic disruption and congestion: ignorance or disregard of traffic signs and

regulations promotes traffic disorder and creating traffic bottlenecks. Many vehicle drivers in Nigeria commonly ignore traffic signs and engage in illegal actions like driving against traffic and other violations. Impatience and lack of discipline create and compound traffic bottlenecks especially at major intersections and high traffic corridors. This is a common cause of traffic holdup in Nigerian cities, including Ilorin.

v. Economic and social costs: economic cost of accidents and congestions likely to result from violation of traffic signs and regulations in the area can be viewed in different forms. These may be seen in terms of medical expenses and property damage. The medical expenses relate to emergency services, hospital care and rehabilitation. For instance, in a study on Ilorin Ibrahim et al (2017) noted that the cost of management of injuries in emergency room patients represents a significant economic drain to low-income residents of the area. Property damage includes costs of vehicle damage and damage to infrastructure. Other economic costs consist of costs such as loss of productivity as a result

of injuries or death. In addition, the cost of accidents may be seen in terms of social cost related to human suffering, grief and loss of quality of life.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results, it is concluded that commercial bus drivers' knowledge of road signs and their compliance is generally low. This has great negative implications for road safety in the study area. The findings underscore the significance of knowledge of road sign and adherence to traffic regulation as measures for reducing traffic accident and ensuring road safety. It is recommended that stringent measures should be put in place to ensure that only those who are qualified are licensed to drive on the road. This can be achieved by ensuring that all intending drivers pass through accredited driving schools before issuance of drivers' license. Also, there should be periodic road safety sensitization for commercial drivers by relevant road safety agencies to ensure familiarity with traffic signs and regulations for effective compliance to reduce road crashes. There should also be stricter enforcement of traffic laws and prosecution of violators, particularly those who ignore signs.

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